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DEPARTMENT OF SUSTAINABLE
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Joining of ageing resistant structures out of light metals and carbon composites by ultrasonics

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Clamping device for torsional US welding

$$W_{US} = \int P_{US} dt$$

Ageing resistant Aluminium/FRP - Concepts

Calculated surface plot of ultimate lap shear force in dependency of welding parameters Welding Force and Oscillation Amplitude and specimen geometry

Welding Energy $W_{US} = 4300 \text{ Ws}$

Monotonic properties of aging resistant transition structures – Al/(GF)-CFRP

[F. Staab, F. Balle: Ultrasonics, 2019, 93, p. 139 – 144]

Cross sections of joining zone (a), outside areas (b) and areas in the middle of the ring (c).

[F. Staab, F. Balle: Ultrasonics, 2019, 93, p. 139 – 144]

Welding power-time-temperature profile | AA5024/(GF)-CF-PEEK

[F. Staab, F. Balle: Ultrasonics, 2019, 93, p. 139 – 144]

Fracture surface analysis by SEM | AA5024/(GF)-CF-PEEK @ Point 3 (a) and Point 4 (b)

[F. Staab, F. Balle: Ultrasonics, 2019, 93, p. 139 – 144]

Measurement of the electrical transition resistance | Al/CFRP-Joints

Hameg Instruments CCR Bridge HM8118

AA5024/(GF)-CF-PEEK

AA5024/CF-PEEK

USS-Parameter:

$$W_{US} = 4300 \text{ Ws}$$

$$F_{US} = 290 \text{ N}$$

$$u = 40 \mu\text{m}$$

References and further reading

- F. Staab, F. Balle: Ultrasonic torsion welding of ageing-resistant Al/CFRP joints: Properties, microstructure and joint formation, 2019, Ultrasonics, 93, p. 139 – 144
- F. Lionetto, C. Mele, P. Leo, S. D'Ostuni, F. Balle, A. Maffezzoli: Ultrasonic spot welding of carbon fiber reinforced epoxy composites to aluminum: mechanical and electrochemical characterization, 2018 Composites Part B-eng, 144, p. 134 – 142
- F. Lionetto, F. Balle, A. Maffezzoli: Hybrid ultrasonic spot welding of aluminum to carbon fiber reinforced epoxy composites, 2017 Journal of Materials Processing Technology, 247, p. 289 – 295
- G. Wagner, F. Balle, D. Eifler: Ultrasonic welding of aluminum alloys to fiber reinforced polymers, 2013 Advanced Engineering Materials, 15 (9), p. 792 – 803
- F. Balle, S. Huxhold, S. Emrich, G. Wagner, M. Kopnarski, D. Eifler; Influence of Heat Treatments on the Mechanical Properties of Ultrasonic Welded AA 2024/CF-PA66-Joints, 2013, Advanced Engineering Materials, Band: 15 (9), p. 837 - 845

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